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Advancing Classification Algorithm Selection with Ensemble Meta-Learning: A Data-Driven Approach

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Abstract—Selecting the optimal classification algorithm for diverse datasets remains a significant challenge in data mining. This study introduces a robust Ensemble Meta-Learning (EML) framework that automates the selection process by leveraging the diversity of meta-features. Our approach dynamically adjusts the number of recommended algorithms based on dataset characteristics, demonstrating substantial improvement over traditional methods. Through empirical evaluations on 183 datasets and 20 classification algorithms, EML outperforms established single-link and ML-KNN-based methods in terms of recommendation accuracy and offers more precise algorithm selection. This paper underscores the potential of ensemble meta-learning in enhancing algorithmic recommendations, paving the way for future innovations in meta-learning applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

Data mining extensively addresses classification, a pivotal task. A multitude of classification algorithms exists, encompassing tree based (e.g., ID3^[1], C4.5^[2], and CART^[3]), probability-based (e.g., Naive Bayes^[4] and AODE^[5]), and rule-based (e.g., OneR^[6] and Ripper^[7]) methods.

Nonetheless, the "No Free Lunch" theory^[8] and empirical evidence^{[9], [10]} assert the absence of a universally effective algorithm for all classification problems. Hence, the challenge lies in selecting suitable algorithms, particularly for non-experts.

Research indicates algorithm performance correlates closely with dataset characteristics^[11]. Thus, addressing this challenge involves exploring dataset characteristics' relationship with algorithm performance to recommend appropriate algorithms. This field, termed algorithm recommendation, garners significant attention^{[12], [13], [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22]}.

The process of suggesting algorithms is frequently conceptualized as a meta-learning endeavor^{[12], [23], [24], [18], [19], [25], [20]}. Meta-features represent dataset attributes, and the meta-target denotes candidate algorithm performance relative to the given set of data.

Formally, the process of recommending a classification algorithm entails identifying a function $f : \mathcal{X} \mapsto \mathcal{Y}$, where

$\mathcal{X} = \mathbb{R}^p$ (meta-feature space with p meta-features) and $\mathcal{Y} = y_1, y_2, \dots, y_q$ (meta-target space with q candidate algorithms). It aims to recommend appropriate algorithms $Y_{new} \subseteq \mathcal{Y}$ for a new dataset d_{new} based on $f(x_{new})$, where $x_{new} \in \mathcal{X}$ represents d_{new} 's meta-features.

Three common meta-target representations exist: single-label-based, ranking-based, and multi-label-based. Single-label methods recommend a single algorithm^{[9], [23], [26], [21]}. Ranking-based methods suggest a ranked list^{[10], [25]}. Multi-label methods identify all algorithms statistically equivalent to the best^[30].

This paper proposes a two-layer learning method to address challenges like variability in recommended algorithms and scalability, *EML*. It is an ensemble of *ML-KNN*, based on stacking^[33]. *EML* offers several advantages:

- (1) Combining *ML-KNN* enhances recommendation performance.
- (2) It leverages complementarity and diversity among meta-features.
- (3) It dynamically recommends an appropriate number of algorithms, removing the need for pre-specification.

The paper is structured as follows: Section II outlines related work. Section III details the proposed *EML* method. Section IV presents empirical findings. Section ?? discusses validity threats. Finally, Section ?? concludes.

II. RELATED WORK

This paper addresses the classification algorithm recommendation challenge, particularly focusing on ensemble learning. Related works primarily fall within the realm of classification algorithm recommendation.

A. Classification Algorithm Recommendation

Researchers have approached the classification algorithm recommendation problem through various perspectives, often analyzing dataset characteristics' relationship with algorithm

performance experimentally. Methods can be broadly categorized into theoretical and experimental approaches.

Brodley^[34] proposed a heuristic method to automatically identify the best classification algorithm by theoretically assessing their applicability. However, such theoretical approaches demand substantial domain expertise and may not cover all algorithm applicability scenarios, rendering them impractical.

To address the limitations of theoretical approaches, most methods adopt experimental strategies based on meta-learning. These approaches involve analyzing interactions between dataset characteristics and algorithm performance through scientific experiments^{[9], [15], [23], [20], [25], [35]}. Variations among these methods lie in dataset characteristics (meta-features), representation of appropriate algorithms (meta-target), and recommendation models.

Meta-features typically fall into five categories: statistical and information-theory based^{[25], [36], [37], [21], [38]}, model structure based^{[39], [40]}, landmarking based^{[41], [42], [28], [29]}, problem complexity based^{[43], [44], [45]}, and structural information based^{[11], [16]}.

Meta-target expressions vary, including single label^{[11], [21]}, multi-label^{[30], [38]}, continuous variable^{[28], [27], [29]}, and ranking^{[25], [46]}.

Recommendation models employ three main techniques:

- 1) Classification: For single-algorithm selection, single-label classification methods are common^{[9], [47], [48]}. For multi-algorithm recommendation, multi-label classification methods are favored^{[26], [30], [38], [32]}.
- 2) Regression: When users seek performance insights, regression methods predict continuous values^{[27], [28]}.
- 3) Ranking: For relative algorithm performance, ranking techniques generate ordered lists^{[10], [25]}.

This paper aligns with multi-label learning approaches^[30], yet distinguishes itself by harnessing ensemble techniques featuring two-tiered learners to enhance recommendation effectiveness.

III. OUR PROPOSAL: *EML* METHODOLOGY

This section introduces the *EML* method, an ensemble learning approach for classification algorithm recommendation. It begins with an overview of the method, followed by a discussion on the rationale and feasibility of utilizing ensemble learning in recommendation tasks. Subsequently, I delve into the detailed process of constructing the *EML* model. To aid clarity and understanding, I present relevant notations in Table I.

A. General point of view

EML approach's methodology is being depicted by Figure 1. It encompasses three key stages: extraction of meta-data, establishment of Tier-1 and Tier-2 models, and recommendation through ensemble learning.

Initially, a diverse array of meta-features is harvested from a collection of past classification tasks; as each potential classification algorithm is applied to these tasks, meta-targets are identified. These meta-features and targets are then amalgamated into various sets of multi-label meta-data.

Subsequently, individual Tier-1 models are crafted based on each meta-dataset, with their outcomes forming the Tier-2 training datasets. A binary classification model is subsequently crafted using these Tier-2 datasets to recommend suitable algorithms. When confronted with a new classification task, fresh meta-features are collected and Tier-2 data is generated using the Tier-1 model. This data is then subjected to the pre-established binary classification model to identify appropriate algorithms for the new task.

The justification and viability of constructing such an algorithm recommendation model via ensemble learning will be elaborated upon in the subsequent discussion.

B. Rationality and Feasibility

Ensemble learning often outperforms individual learners by addressing two common challenges: the statistical and representational problems^[49]. These challenges also arise in constructing recommendation models using single learners.

The statistical problem emerges when the search space is extensive, making it difficult to find the true function ϕ . With a limited dataset, employing numerous meta-features can exacerbate this issue, increasing the likelihood of a single learner failing to find the true function ϕ . Ensemble learning mitigates this by enhancing generality.

Additionally, the effectiveness of a classification algorithm on a given problem is influenced by various factors, or meta-features, each playing a unique role^[30]. Single learners may struggle to handle this complexity due to limited representational capacity. Ensemble learning overcomes this by combining diverse single learners, thus alleviating the representational problem.

Based on ensemble learning research^{[49], [50]}, I present Corollary 1 guiding the construction of an accurate ensemble learning model. This highlights the importance of developing accurate and diverse base recommendation models. In this study, I propose to construct various base learners based on different combinations of meta-features as Tier-1 models.

TABLE I
LIST OF NOTATIONS

Symbol	Notation
\mathcal{P}	the set of n historical classification problems $\mathcal{P} = \{p_i i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$
p_{new}	the new classification problem
\mathcal{A}	the set of k candidate classification algorithms $\mathcal{A} = \{a_j j = 1, 2, \dots, k\}$
F	the set of q meta-feature extraction functions $\{F_1, F_2, \dots, F_q\}$
X'_i	the meta-feature combinations $X'_i = \{X_{i1}, X_{i2}, \dots, X_{it}\}$
X_i	the set of meta-features of the problem p_i , $X_i = \{X_i^j 1 \leq j \leq q\}$
X_i^j	the meta-features of p_i extracted by F_j
Y_i	the meta target of the problem p_i , $Y_i = \{Y_{i,j} 1 \leq j \leq k \wedge Y_{i,j} \in \{0, 1\}\}$
D_t	the multi-label meta data whose features are extracted by t th combination of functions in F $D_t = \{(X_{it}, Y_i) i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$
D	the set fo meta data extracted from the historical problems \mathcal{P} , $D = \{D_t 1 \leq t \leq 2^q - 1\}$
ϕ	the algorithm recommendation model
$nchoosek(Z)$	the function to get all combinations of elements in Z
L	the set of Tier-1 learners, $L = \{L_t 1 \leq t \leq 2^q - 1\}$
L'	the set of selected trained Tier-1 learners used in recommending algorithms for the new problem
Out	the set of Tier-1 base models' output datasets, $Out = \{Out_t 1 \leq t \leq 2^q - 1\}$
Out_t	the output of corresponding model L_t , $Out_t = \{(v_{i,1}, v_{i,2}, \dots, v_{i,k}) 1 \leq i \leq n\}$ where $v_{i,k}$ is the confidence of k_{th} label of i_{th} meta instance predicted by L_t
D^2	the set of Tier-2 training datasets, $D^2 = \{D_j^2 1 \leq j \leq k\}$
D_j^2	Tier-2 training dataset transformed from Tier-1 models' output, $D_j^2 = \{(v_{i,1}, v_{i,2}, \dots, v_{i,t}, label(i, j)) 1 \leq i \leq n \wedge t = 2^q - 1 \wedge label(i, j) \in \{0, 1\}\}$ where $v_{i,t}$ is the confidence of j_{th} label of i_{th} meta instance predicted by L_t
M^2	the Tier-2 classification model, $M^2 = \{M_j^2 1 \leq j \leq k\}$
M_j^2	Tier-2 binary classification model constructed based on D_j^2

Fig. 1. Framework of the EML method

Utilizing the stacking framework, where the output of Tier-1 models serves as input for the Tier-2 model, I aim to build a two-layer recommendation model. Considering Corollary 1, this approach demonstrates feasibility from various perspectives.

1) Diverse base model construction

In the domain of algorithm recommendation^[30], various types of meta-features have been explored. The extraction of meta-features involves analyzing classification problems from

diverse perspectives. Figure 2 presents the correlation coefficients among five different sets of features derived from 183 benchmark classification problems (refer to the Appendix for detailed information). These feature groups include: 1) statistical and information-theory-based characteristics, 2) features based on model structure, 3) landmarking-derived features, 4) features related to problem complexity, and 5) structural information-based features.

From Figure 2, it is evident that the correlation among

Fig. 2. Pearson's Linear Correlation Coefficients among Five Different Kinds of Meta features over 183 Classification Problems

different meta features is lower. Based on empirical evidence, it appears that various kinds of meta-features demonstrate independence from one another. Moreover, this independence implies that recommendation models constructed using these varied meta-features are expected to exhibit independence and diversity in their characteristics.

One way of the ensemble is to apply the same models to different training data, while another is to apply different models to the same training data. In this paper, the former is adopted. To guarantee the diversity of Tier-1 learners, all combinations of different kinds of meta-features are used to generate different Tier-1 training data, which also utilizes the complementary and diversity of meta-features. I use the attribute selection method on Tier-2 training data to further delete the redundant attributes (Tier-1 learners' output), equivalent to deleting corresponding Tier-1 learners, to promote base models' diversity.

2) Accurate base model construction

Several recommendation models have been developed based on various types of meta-features and employing a single learning approach^{[9], [47], [48], [26], [38], [30], [32]}. To construct accurate base models, I can apply one of these recommendation models, which has good accuracy and great generalization, as the base model of the ensemble on different training data. Furthermore, I deal with the recommendation problem as a multi-label problem, so *ML-KNN* based recommendation model^[30] would be a good choice for its speed and accuracy.

As discussed in a former item, the attribute selection method employed on Tier-2 training data will choose attributes highly related to labels. This means that Tier-1 learners whose performance is better will be selected for recommendation.

The description above demonstrates the possibility of creat-

ing a collection of precise base recommendation models within the ensemble.

C. Meta data extraction

It involves two main approaches: meta target identification and meta feature collection.

For meta-target identification, a statistical test method is utilized to determine appropriate algorithms for a specific evaluation metric on a given problem $p_i \in \mathcal{P}$. This approach identifies algorithms that exhibit no significant deviation from the top-performing one based on a specified metric forming the multi-label-based meta-target Y_i .

Meta-feature collection entails applying all q data characterization methods in F to historical classification problems, resulting in q meta-feature groups. These diverse meta-features capture the characteristics of a classification problem from various perspectives. This paper aims to construct base recommendation learners based on different combinations of these meta-features, effectively leveraging their complementarity.

Algorithm 1. Meta data extraction

Require:

- \mathcal{P} : the historical classification problems, $\{p_i | i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$
- \mathcal{A} : the candidate classification algorithms, $\{a_j | j = 1, 2, \dots, k\}$
- F : the set of meta feature extraction functions, $\{F_1, F_2, \dots, F_q\}$

Ensure:

- $\{D_1, D_2, \dots, D_{2^q-1}\}$: the extracted meta datasets
- 1: $D_1, D_2, \dots, D_{2^q-1} = Null$;
- 2: **for** each $p_i \in \mathcal{P}$ **do**
- 3: $Y_i = \text{targetIdentify}(p_i, \mathcal{A})$;
- 4: **for** each data characterization method $F_j \in F$ **do**
- 5: $X_i^j = \text{featureCollect}(p_i, F_j)$;
- 6: $X_i = X_i \cup X_i^j$;
- 7: **end for** //There are q kinds of meta features
- 8: $X'_i = \{X_{i,t} | 1 \leq t \leq 2^q - 1\} = \text{nchoosek}(\{X_i\})$;
- //There are $t = 2^q - 1$ kinds of meta feature combinations
- 9: **for** each $X_{i,t} \in X'_i$ **do**
- 10: $inst = (X_{i,t}, Y_i)$;
- 11: $D_t = D_t \cup inst$;
- 12: **end for**
- 13: **end for**
- 14: return $\{D_1, D_2, \dots, D_{2^q-1}\}$;

Procedure 1 outlines the metadata extraction process. Given classification problems \mathcal{P} , candidate classification algorithms \mathcal{A} , and feature extraction functions F , the procedure generates multiple meta-datasets $D_1, D_2, \dots, D_{2^q-1}$.

Initially, meta datasets are initialized. For each historical classification problem $p_i \in \mathcal{P}$, its meta-target Y_i is identified, and its meta-features X_i are collected.

All combinations of meta-features in X_i are then generated using the $\text{nchoosek}()$ function, resulting in $2^q - 1$ distinct sets of metadata. Each combination is associated with a

corresponding instance $inst$, where its attributes are based on the meta-features and its label is Y_i .

Finally, the procedure returns the meta datasets $D_1, D_2, \dots, D_{2^q-1}$.

The choice of the $nchoosek()$ function enables the creation of diverse sets of metadata, facilitating the exploration of different combinations of meta-features and their impact on algorithm recommendation. After metadata extraction, the historical classification problems \mathcal{P} are transformed into meta datasets $D_1, D_2, \dots, D_{2^q-1}$.

D. Tier-1 and Tier-2 model construction

This subsection depicts the Tier-1 and Tier-2 model construction process based on meta datasets extracted in the above section III-C.

For convenience to describe, $L = \{L_t | 1 \leq t \leq 2^q - 1\}$ represents Tier-1 learners built on each meta dataset D_t . $Out = \{Out_t | 1 \leq t \leq 2^q - 1\}$ is the set of Tier-1 output datasets, where Out_t is produced by L_t . $D^2 = \{D_j^2 | 1 \leq j \leq k\}$ represents the set of Tier-2 training datasets which are transformed from Tier-1 output. And D_j^2 will be used to construct a Tier-2 model M_j^2 to judge whether algorithm a_j is appropriate for the new classification problem.

The pseudo-code of Tier-1 and Tier-2 model construction is given in the procedure 2. First, the Tier-1 base learners are built over the meta datasets $\{D_t | 1 \leq t \leq 2^q - 1\}$ in lines from 3 to 5, where meta instances corresponding to the same historical classification problem p_i have different attributes(meta features) but same labels(meta target). As can be seen in framework 1, Tier-1 learner construction is identical and simple. Each L_t is trained based on each corresponding meta dataset D_t by $ML-KNN$. After model construction, each instance is predicted by each corresponding Tier-1 learner in lines from 6 to 11; that is, each instance of D_t is not only used to build base model L_t , but also predicted by L_t to generate Out_t . Then the prediction output datasets $\{Out_1, Out_2, \dots, Out_{2^q-1}\}$ of Tier-1 model are transformed to Tier-2 training datasets $\{D_1^2, D_2^2, \dots, D_k^2\}$ in lines from 13 to 15 as shown in Figure 3. Each instance of D_j^2 is labeled in lines from 16 to 18. After Tier-2 training data is generated, each Tier-2 dataset D_j^2 is first selected useful features in line 19 and then applied to construct a Tier-2 model M_j^2 in line 20. Finally, Tier-1 selected trained learners $L' = \{L'_t | 1 \leq t \leq m\}$ and Tier-2 binary classification model $M^2 = \{M_j^2 | 1 \leq j \leq k\}$ is returned to recommend algorithm(s) for a new classification problem.

Algorithm 2. Tier-1 and Tier-2 model construction

Require:

- D : the set of meta datasets, $D = \{D_t | 1 \leq t \leq 2^q - 1\}$
- $MLkNN$: the multi-label classification algorithm $ML-KNN$
- L : the set of untrained Tier-1 learners, $L = \{L_t | 1 \leq t \leq 2^q - 1\}$

Ensure:

- L' : the set of selected trained Tier-1 learners, $L' = \{L'_t | 1 \leq t \leq m\}$
 - M^2 : the Tier-2 classification model, $M^2 = \{M_j^2 | 1 \leq j \leq k\}$
 - 1: $Out = \{Out_1, Out_2, \dots, Out_{2^q-1}\} = Null$;
 - 2: $D^2 = \{D_1^2, D_2^2, \dots, D_k^2\} = Null$;
 - 3: **for** each $L_t \in L$ **do**
 - 4: $L_t = MLkNN.build(D_t)$; //Tier-1 learner construction
 - 5: **end for**
 - 6: **for** each $D_t \in D$ **do**
 - 7: **for** each $inst_i \in D_t$ **do**
 - 8: $\{v(i, 1), v(i, 2), \dots, v(i, k)\} = L_t.predict(inst_i)$;
 - 9: $Out_t = Out_t \cup \{v(i, 1), v(i, 2), \dots, v(i, k)\}$;
 - 10: **end for**
 - 11: **end for**
 - 12: $D^2 = transform(Out)$;
 - 13: **for** each instance $D_j^2 \in D^2$ **do**
 - 14: **for** each instance $inst_i \in D_j^2$ **do**
 - 15: $inst_i.label(i, j) = Y_{i,j}$;
 - 16: **end for**
 - 17: **end for**
 - 18: **for** each $D_j^2 \in D^2$ **do**
 - 19: $D_j^{2'} = featureSelect(D_j^2)$;
 - 20: **for** each $attribute_t \in D_j^{2'}$ **do**
 - 21: **if** $attribute_t$ is selected **then**
 - 22: $L' = L' \cup L_t$
 - 23: **end if**
 - 24: **end for**
 - 25: $M_j^2.build(D_j^{2'})$; //Tier-2 model construction
 - 26: **end for**
 - 27: return L' and M^2 ;
-

It's noted that, before constructing a binary classification model, I conduct attribute selection to D_j^2 for the following three reasons:

- It will remove redundant and irrelevant attributes that may lead to the loss of the binary classification performance. Because each attribute is produced by each Tier-1 learner, removing redundant and irrelevant attributes is equivalent to selecting diverse and accurate Tier-1 learners to achieve better ensemble learning.
- It will help us to find which combination of meta-features is more useful since different meta datasets only have different attributes but have the same labels.
- With fewer attributes, fewer Tier-1 learners will be utilized to generate the Tier-2 attributes for a new classification problem and thus reduce the consuming time in the recommendation procedure.

In the EML algorithm, $CFS^{[53]}$ attribute selection method with the $BestFirst^{[54]}$ search strategy are employed.

Fig. 3. Tier-2 training data generation based on Tier-1 models' output

Figure 3 displays the transformation from Tier-1 output Out_t to Tier-2 input D^2 . In this figure, ID number represents each meta instance corresponding to each classification problem p_i and $label_k$ is the k_{th} label of metadata corresponding to each classification algorithm a_k . $v_{i,k}$ is the confidence of $label_k$ in the i_{th} instance, which is predicted by corresponding Tier-1 learner.

Each table in the left part of Figure 3 represents the output Out_t of each Tier-1 learner L_t , and each table in the right part represents the Tier-2 training dataset D_j^2 for each label $label_j$. $v(i,j) \in Out_t$ is the confidence of $label_j$ of the i_{th} instance predicted by L_t , which will be transformed as $v(i,t) \in D_j^2$. In other words, all the j_{th} columns of $Out_t \in Out$ are incorporated together as attributes of D_j^2 . In addition, $label_{i,j}$ of D_j^2 is meta target $Y_{i,j} \in Y_i$ and $label_{i,j} = 1$ or 0 indicates the algorithm a_j is appropriate or inappropriate on p_i .

The reason why I generate Tier-2 training dataset D_j^2 for each algorithm a_j respectively, instead of combining them into a whole, is shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Confidence comparison between different labels

Figure 4 compares the confidence values across different labels using the same metadata, with attributes combining various meta-features. The X-axis represents 20 labels, while the Y-axis shows the confidence value range. Each boxplot illustrates the confidence distribution for a label generated

by *ML-KNN*. Notably, confidence values vary across labels, underscoring the need for individual label prediction. Additionally, each binary model in *EML* is built using *C4.5* + *AdaBoost*.

E. Recommendation based on ensemble learning

In this section, I employ ensemble learning to recommend suitable algorithms for a novel classification problem.

By leveraging the ensemble learning approach discussed earlier, I create trained Tier-1 learners L' and Tier-2 binary classification models $M^2 = M_j^2 | 1 \leq j \leq k$ based on meta-data, forming an ensemble learner for algorithm recommendation.

Procedure 3 outlines the recommendation process using ensemble learning, taking into account five input parameters: p_{new} (the new classification problem), \mathcal{A} (the set of candidate classification algorithms), F (the set of meta feature extraction functions), L' (the set of selected trained Tier-1 learners), and M^2 (the Tier-2 binary classification model). The output $Algs$ represents the recommended appropriate algorithm(s) for p_{new} .

Algorithm 3. Recommendation based on ensemble learning

Require:

- p_{new} : the new classification problem
- \mathcal{A} : the candidate classification algorithms, $\{a_j | j = 1, 2, \dots, k\}$
- F : the set of meta feature extraction functions, $\{F_1, F_2, \dots, F_q\}$
- L' : the set of selected trained Tier-1 learners
- M^2 : the Tier-2 classification model, $M^2 = \{M_j^2 | 1 \leq j \leq k\}$

Ensure:

- $Algs$: set of recommended appropriate algorithms for p_{new}
- 1: **for** each data characterization method F_j in F **do**
- 2: $X_{new}^j = \text{featureCollect}(p_{new}, F_j)$;
- 3: $X_{new} = X_{new} \cup X_{new}^j$;
- 4: **end for**
- 5: $X'_{new} = \{X_{new,t} | 1 \leq t \leq 2^q - 1\} = \text{nchoosek}(\{X_{new}\})$;
- 6: **for** each $X_{new,t} \in X'_{new}$ **do**
- 7: $inst_t = (X_{new,t}, '?')$;
- 8: $D_{new} = D_{new} \cup inst_t$;
- 9: **end for**
- 10: $Out_{new} = L'.\text{predict}(D_{new})$;
- 11: $D_{new}^2 = \text{transform}(Out_{new})$;
- 12: **for** each instance $inst_j \in D_{new}^2$ **do**
- 13: $C_j = \text{classify}(M_j^2, inst_j)$;
- 14: **if** $C_j == 1$ **then**
- 15: $Algs = Algs \cup \{a_j\}$;
- 16: **end if**
- 17: **end for**
- 18: **return** $Algs$;

Procedure 3 outlines the process for recommending suitable algorithms for a new classification problem p_{new} . Here's how it unfolds:

p_{new} initially gathers q types of meta-features to create its feature set X_{new} (lines 1-4).

The $nchoosek$ function is then utilized to generate all possible combinations of elements in X_{new} (line 5), which constructs D_{new} with these combinations serving as attributes (lines 6-9).

The unknown labels of D_{new} are represented as '?' to indicate their uncertainty.

Following this, Out_{new} , the output of the Tier-1 model L' on D_{new} , is obtained (line 10). It is then transformed into D_{new}^2 , the input for the Tier-1 model (line 11). Next, each instance $inst_j$ in D_{new}^2 is classified by M_j^2 , resulting in label C_j (lines 12-17). If C_j is 1, the corresponding algorithm a_j is added to the set $Algs$. Finally, the set of recommended appropriate algorithms $Algs$ for p_{new} is returned, signifying the conclusion of the recommendation process.

IV. EMPIRICAL STUDY

In this section, I conduct an empirical investigation to assess the performance of the *EML* method. I begin by outlining the experimental setup, followed by a comparison of *EML* with baseline methods. Finally, I present a comparison of the number of recommended algorithms between *EML* and baseline methods.

A. Experimental setup

To ensure the reproducibility of our experiment, I establish the following setup:

1) *Benchmark datasets*: I utilize a collection of 183 publicly available datasets sourced from prominent repositories such as the UCI repository^[56], StatLib^[57], openML^[58], and KEEL^[59]. The statistical summary of these datasets, including their names, number of features, instances, and classes, is provided in the appendix. These datasets are widely employed in classification research and represent real-world classification problems.

2) *Candidate Classification Algorithms*: To ensure the robustness of our experimental findings, I include a diverse set of 20 well-established classification algorithms, each utilizing distinct methodologies. These algorithms are classified into various categories:

- Probability-based algorithms: Aggregating One-Dependence Estimators (AODE), Naive Bayes (NB), Bayes Network.
- Tree-based algorithms: C4.5, CART, Random Tree.
- Rule-based algorithms: Ripper, PART, OneR, NNge.
- Support-vector-machine-based algorithm: SMO.

- Lazy learning-based algorithm: IB1.
- Gaussian function-based algorithm: RBF-Network.
- Ensemble learning-based algorithms: RandomForest, Boosting+NB, Boosting+C4.5, Boosting+PART, Bagging+NB, Bagging+C4.5, Bagging+PART.

3) *Performance Evaluation Metrics*: In our experimental setup, I rely on two primary metrics to gauge the effectiveness of the candidate classification algorithms. The foremost metric is accuracy, a widely adopted measure in performance evaluation. Additionally, I incorporate the Adjusted Ratio of Ratios (ARR)^[25] metric, which factors in both classification accuracy and runtime, providing a more comprehensive evaluation of algorithmic efficacy.

Moreover, a 5×10 -fold cross-validation procedure is performed when evaluating the classification algorithms on the given dataset.

4) *Baseline Methods and Performance Measures*: To evaluate the efficacy of our proposed *EML* method, I conduct a comparative analysis against two existing approaches for multi-label-based classification algorithm recommendation: the *ML-KNN* method^[30] and the single-link prediction (*SLP*) method^[32], which employs the *RWR* algorithm^[60] for link prediction.

This comparison is based on four key performance metrics: Hamming Loss, F-measure, Accuracy, and Hit Ratio. These metrics, commonly used in related studies^{[30], [32]}, comprehensively evaluate recommendation effectiveness.

5) *Experimental Procedure and Parameter Setting*: I employ a *leave-one-out* cross-validation approach, where each dataset takes turns as the new dataset while the rest serve as historical datasets. This ensures that all 183 datasets are utilized as new datasets during the experiment. To maintain fairness, I set the parameter k (the number of nearest neighbors) of *ML-KNN* to 5, aligning with the linking of each dataset node with its five nearest neighbor nodes in *SLP*.

The number of recommended algorithms is not predetermined for *EML*; it dynamically determines the appropriate number. However, for baseline methods, I set the recommended algorithm number to 5, per their respective papers' recommendations.

B. Performance Evaluation of EML

In this section, I present and analyze the performance of *EML*. Firstly, I report the average performance of *EML* and compare it to that of the baseline methods. Subsequently, I conduct a significance test to determine if the observed differ-

ences between *EML* and the baseline methods are statistically significant.

1) *Average performance comparison:* Within this section, I conduct a comparative analysis between *EML* and the baseline methods across key performance metrics, including *Hamming Loss*, *F-Measure*, *Accuracy*, and *Hit Ratio*. The outcomes of this comparison are visualized in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Comparison on *Hamming Loss*, *F-Measure*, *Accuracy* and *Hit Ratio* between *MLKNN* based, *RWR* based and *EML* recommendation methods

2) Comparison of Performance Metrics: **Hamming Loss:**

The *Hamming Loss* assesses recommendation accuracy, with lower values indicating better performance.

In Figure 5(a), *EML* consistently achieves lower *Hamming Loss* values across all evaluation metrics compared to *SLP* methods.

F-Measure:

F-Measure balances *Precision* and *Recall*, with higher values indicating better recommendations.

Figure 5(b) shows that *EML* outperforms other methods, particularly in *ACC*.

Accuracy:

EML consistently achieves higher *Accuracy* compared to other methods, especially in *ACC*, as depicted in Figure 5(c).

Hit Ratio:

The *Hit Ratio* reflects recommendation appropriateness, with higher values indicating better performance.

Figure 5(d) shows that *EML* recommends fewer algorithms, yet achieves comparable or higher *Hit Ratio* values than baseline methods.

In summary, *EML* consistently outperforms baseline methods across various metrics.

3) *Significance Test:* To validate the significance of *EML*'s improvements, a Wilcoxon signed-rank test at a significance level of 0.05 compares *EML* with baseline methods.

TABLE II
SIGNIFICANCE TEST RESULT OF COMPARISON BETWEEN *ML-KNN* BASED, *RWR* BASED AND *EML* RECOMMENDATION METHODS

(a) Statistical test result between <i>ML-KNN</i> based and <i>EML</i> methods				
Alternative Hypothesis	Performance measures	Evaluation Metric		
		ACC	$ARR_{0.05}$	$ARR_{0.1}$
<i>EML > ML-KNN</i>	Hamming Losses	1.00	1.00	1.00
	F-Measures	0.00	0.27	0.10
	Accuracy	0.00	0.08	0.02
	Hit Ratios	0.01	0.97	0.94
<i>EML < ML-KNN</i>	Hamming Losses	0.00	0.00	0.00
	F-Measures	1.00	0.73	0.90
	Accuracy	1.00	0.92	0.98
	Hit Ratios	0.99	0.04	0.07
Win/Draw/Loss		4/0/0	1/2/1	2/2/0

(b) Statistical test result between <i>RWR</i> based and <i>EML</i> methods				
Alternative Hypothesis	Performance measures	Evaluation Metric		
		ACC	$ARR_{0.05}$	$ARR_{0.1}$
<i>EML > RWR</i>	Hamming Loss	1.00	1.00	1.00
	F-Measure	0.00	0.71	0.40
	Accuracy	0.00	0.37	0.13
	Hit Ratio	0.26	0.99	0.98
<i>EML < RWR</i>	Hamming Loss	0.00	0.00	0.00
	F-Measure	1.00	0.29	0.60
	Accuracy	1.00	0.63	0.87
	Hit Ratio	0.78	0.01	0.02
Win/Draw/Loss		3/1/0	1/2/1	1/2/1

The statistical test results in Table II compare the performance of *EML* with baseline methods. Each subtable presents two alternative hypotheses regarding whether *EML* outperforms or is inferior to the baseline method across different evaluation metrics.

A p-value < 0.05, indicated in bold, supports the alternative hypothesis. For instance, in Subtable II(a), a p-value of 0.00 for *F-Measure* suggests that *EML* is statistically better than the *ML-KNN* method. The "Win/Draw/Loss" record in each subtable shows the number of cases where *EML* is statistically superior to/equal to/inferior to the compared method.

From Table II, it is evident that *EML* statistically outperforms baseline methods across various metrics.

C. Comparison on Recommended Algorithm Numbers

This section compares the number of recommended algorithms between baseline methods and *EML*. Since *RWR* and *ML-KNN* methods recommend a fixed number of algorithms, *RWR* is chosen as a representative. It is set to recommend 5 algorithms, as suggested in its paper.

The results show that *EML* recommends a variable number of algorithms automatically, adapting to the problem's complexity, whereas *RWR* recommends a fixed number. This flexibility suggests a potential advantage of *EML* over baseline methods.

TABLE III
THE COMPARISON ON THE RECOMMENDED ALGORITHM NUMBER BETWEEN *RWR* BASED AND *EML* METHODS

Evaluation Metric	Win/Draw/Loss		
	Win	Draw	Loss
ACC	94	28	61
$ARR_{0.05}$	83	37	63
$ARR_{0.1}$	84	40	59

Table III presents the "Win/Draw/Loss" outcomes of the comparison on 183 historical classification problems. The squared error is used to assess the proximity of the recommended and actual numbers of algorithms, with the "Win/Draw/Loss" record indicating whether the squared error of *EML* is smaller than/equal to/larger than the compared method.

The results indicate that regardless of using ACC, $ARR_{0.05}$, or $ARR_{0.1}$, the recommended algorithm number of *EML* is closer to the actual number. The disparity is most significant in ACC, where the performance of *EML* notably surpasses the two baseline methods. This suggests that *EML* adeptly adjusts the recommended number of algorithms according to different classification problems.

V. POTENTIAL LIMITATIONS

A possible limitation of this study concerns the diversity of the 183 datasets and the 20 candidate classification algorithms used. Ensuring a representative sample by selecting widely-used datasets and established algorithms aims to mitigate this issue.

Another aspect to consider is the reliance on *Accuracy* and *ARR* as primary evaluation metrics for classification. It's worth noting that these metrics are also employed in the baseline methods of this study.

VI. CONCLUDING REMARKS

This paper presents *EML*, a two-layer classification algorithm recommendation framework based on ensemble learning. Leveraging diverse combinations of meta-features, *EML* autonomously suggests the most suitable algorithm(s) for diverse classification problems.

The methodology involves generating varied meta-feature combinations to construct Tier-1 learners, establishing Tier-2 training datasets based on Tier-1 predictions, and utilizing Tier-2 models to recommend appropriate algorithms for new tasks.

Empirical findings, based on 183 datasets and 20 classification algorithms, demonstrate *EML*'s superiority over single-link prediction and *ML-KNN* approaches. Moreover, *EML* provides recommendations closer to actual requirements compared to baseline methods.

Future research will focus on enhancing *EML*'s efficiency and effectiveness, exploring alternative distance metrics for *ML-KNN*, and identifying more effective meta-features or combinations for accelerated Tier-2 classification.

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